

INFLUENCE OF FABRICATION CONDITIONS ON PROPERTIES OF PLA/PBAT WOOD COMPOSITE STRAND

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1 Introduction

Natural rattan has been used in the manufacture of furniture, baskets and other articles for many centuries. The various species of rattan range from several millimeters up to 5–7 cm in diameter. From a strand of rattan, the skin is usually peeled off, to be used as rattan weaving material. The remaining "core" of the rattan can be used for various purposes in furniture making. Furniture manufactured from rattan offers greater comfort than furniture manufactured from solid woods because of its inherent compliancy. Further, it is light weight and reasonably strong, making it an important material in the manufacture of furniture. However, natural rattan has had limited use in the outdoor furniture market since it softens and weakens when wet, and is more susceptible to rotting and mildew than many other natural and man-made furniture materials. Also, its shortage in nowadays supply leads manufacturer to produce synthetic strands made of plastics to replace natural ones. Most of synthetic strands are prepared from low-density polyethylene, high-density polyethylene, polyvinyl chloride, polyethylene terephthalate, and polyamide, which some of them have been granted patents for either compositions, processing, or methods to product articles from synthetic strands [1].

Nowadays, poly(lactic acid) or PLA becomes one of the main biodegradable polymers which have been interested to replace commodity synthetic polymers. PLA is linear, aliphatic thermoplastic polyester with rigidity and clarity similar to polystyrene (PS) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET). It is used for different applications ranging from medical to packaging, resorbable and biodegradable under industrial composting conditions. Generally, PLA is made into useful items using thermal processes like injection molding and extrusion. Unfortunately, high brittleness of PLA is the major issue for its applications. Blending PLA with flexible biodegradable polymers such as poly (butylene

adipate-co-terephthalate) or PBAT would provide the blend with desired flexibility. PBAT is aliphatic-aromatic copolyester, which is fully biodegradable and flexible plastic designed for film extrusion. In the view of its high toughness and biodegradability, PBAT is considered as a good candidate for the toughness of PLA. Kumar et al. [2] prepared PLA/PBAT blend and its nanocomposites using melt blending technique. Glycidylmethacrylate (GMA) was used as a reactive compatibilizer to improve the interface between PLA and PBAT. Mechanical studies indicated an increase in impact strength and tensile modulus of PLA matrix with the increase in PBAT loading. PLA/PBAT blend prepared at ratio of 75/25 wt% exhibited optimum impact strength. Further, incorporation of GMA to the tune of 5 wt% and nanoclay shows an increase of impact strength. Pivsa-Art et al. [3] blended PLA, PBSA, and PBAT in order to prepare blown film. The ratio of PLA and PBSA was fixed at 80/20 and the PBAT content was investigated with 0, 10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 wt%. It was found that the melt flow index and tensile strength of blends decreased with increasing amount of PBAT, whereas the percentage strain showed contrastive results. The maximum tensile strength and impact strength were reached with the blend of equal amount 20 wt% of PBAT.

PLA, PBAT, and blend between PLA and PBAT have been prepared wood composites in order to produce biodegradable composites. Bodros et al. [4] studied tensile properties of natural fiber-biopolymer composites in order to determine whether or not, biocomposites may replace glass fiber reinforced unsaturated polyester resins, which are mainly used for fitting-up products in the automotive industry. The materials used are flax fiber, polylactic acid (PLA), L-poly lactide acid (PLLA), poly(3-hydroxyl butyrate) (PHB), polycaprolactone and starch thermoplastic (MaterBite[®]Z), poly(butylene succinate) (PBS) and poly(butylene adipate-co-terephthalate) (PBAT). Their preliminary results show that the tensile properties are improved with

the fiber volume fraction. The tensile strength and Young's modulus of PLLA and PLA flax composites are greater than those of similar PP/flax fiber composites. The specific tensile strength and modulus of flax fiber/PLLA composite have proved to be very close to those of glass fiber polyester composites. Anith Liyana Mohd Sis et al [5] studied wood fiber composite made of PLA/PBAT/kenaf fiber using melt blending method. A PLA/PBAT blend with the ratio of 90/10 wt%, and the same blend ratio reinforced with various amounts of kenaf fiber were prepared and characterized. The addition of kenaf fiber would reduce mechanical properties of composites sharply due to the poor interaction between the fiber and polymer matrix. Modification of the composite by (3-aminopropyl) trimethoxy silane (APTMS) showed improvements in mechanical properties, increasing up to 42.46, 62.71 and 22.00 % for tensile strength, flexural strength and impact strength, respectively.

In order to ease the optimization process by limiting the number of experiments, employing statistical methods such as the Taguchi design of experiment (DOE) approach could be very useful. The procedure is a factorial DOE method which avoids the great number of experiments required for a full factorial design study and can be used for modelling and analyzing the influence of control factors on performance output. The concept of signal/noise ratio is a measure of the robustness of the design and helps the investigators to identify the optimal combination of factors to achieve the targeted mean value of the property under study, with the least variability. Pishbin et al [6] implemented a study of the Taguchi design method to optimize the rate of electrophoretic deposition (EPD) of Bioglass® particles from aqueous suspensions. The effect of Bioglass® concentration, pH and electric field was investigated. An orthogonal array of L16 type with mixed levels of the control factors was utilized. Their experimental results and statistical analyses were discussed based on the current knowledge of the EPD of ceramic materials.

Since the viscosity of suspensions depends strongly on the properties of the applied particles like particle size, particle size distribution, and solid load and especially on the specific surface area, Asghari and Gopalsamy et al [7] applied Taguchi method to find optimum process parameters for end milling while hard machining of hardened steel. A L18 array, signal-to-noise ratio and analysis of variance (ANOVA) are applied to study performance

characteristics of machining parameters (cutting speed, feed, depth of cut and width of cut) with consideration of surface finish and tool life. Chipping and adhesion are observed to be main causes of wear. Results obtained by Taguchi method match closely with ANOVA and cutting speed is most influencing parameter. Multiple regression equations are formulated for estimating predicted values of surface roughness and tool wear.

In the previous study [8], light-weight synthetic rattan from composites between high-density polyethylene (HDPE), ethylene-propylene-diene elastomer (EPDM), and Pinewood fibers was prepared. Wood fiber content and silane coupling agent were varied to study their effect on physical and mechanical properties. A chemical blowing agent with several contents was incorporated in order to produce fine foaming structure inside composite strands. Based on Young's modulus, strains at ultimate stress and its color, the optimized wood content was 2 phr with silane treatment of 2.5 wt% of wood weight. Densities of foamed composite strands synthetic rattan had lower non-foamed ones. L* in Lab system of foamed composite strands was somewhat higher than non-foamed ones and were closed to natural rattan.

In this present work, we have attempted to prepare synthetic rattan from biodegradable PLA and PBAT blend adding Pinewood fibers and found that the fabrication condition is so crucial for good quality synthetic strand. We have obtained the process window for fabrication the biodegradable wood-plastic composite strands; however, they have impact on appearance as well as properties. This study thus aims to investigate influence of fabrication conditions, such as die temperature, water bath (cooling) temperature, and puller speed, on diameter and tensile properties of biodegradable wood-plastic composite strands. The design of experiment (DOE) via Taguchi method was conducted in order to investigate influence of these factors statistically. An orthogonal array of L9 type with mixed levels of the fabrication parameters was utilized, and the signal/noise ratio was used to determine the most influencing parameter for the fabrication conditions.

2 Experimental 2.1 Materials

PLA (Ingeo 2003D) was purchased from Nature Work LLC, USA. PBAT (FBX 7011) was purchased from BASF, Germany. Pinewood fibers (200 mesh size) were supplied by Linpai Co., China. 3-amino

propyltriethoxy silane (APTES) from Sigma-Aldrich was used as coupling agent.

2.2 Silane treatment of Pinewood fibers

Dried Pinewood fibers were treated with APTES silane solution using 6 wt% silane with respect to fiber weight in 95/5 v/v% ethanol/water solution. Silane-treated Pinewood fibers were dried in a vacuum oven at 120°C for 24 hrs.

2.3 Strand fabrication with design of experiment (DOE) via Taguchi method

Prior compounding, PLA and PBAT was dried thoroughly using an air-circulating oven at 50 °C. Under the same composition, PLA/PBAT and dried silane-treated Pinewood fibers were melt blending in a twin-screw extruder (SHJ-25, Yongteng, China) through a rod die with diameter of 4 mm. Wood composite strands were pulled out by a puller and cooled in water bath. The design of experiment via Taguchi method using an orthogonal L9 array was applied and presented in Table 1. Other factors such as screw speed and barrel temperature were kept constant. The statistical analysis was performed using Minitab® ver.15.

Table 1. Orthogonal L9 array for DOE experiment.

	Abbreviation	Die temp. (°C)	Water bath temp. (°C)	Puller speed (cm/s)
A	D160W30S0.6	160	30	0.6
B	D160W35S0.8	160	35	0.8
C	D160W40S1.0	160	40	1.0
D	D165W30S0.8	165	30	0.8
E	D165W35S1.0	165	35	1.0
F	D165W40S0.6	165	40	0.6
G	D170W30S1.0	170	30	1.0
H	D170W35S0.6	170	35	0.6
I	D170W40S0.8	170	40	0.8

2.4 Diameter measurement of PLA/PBAT/Pine wood fiber strands

Diameter of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands of 20 cm long was measured 3 points along its length using a digital Venier caliper. Ten specimens of each fabrication condition were measured their diameter, and the average and standard deviation was calculated.

2.5 Lightness measurement of PLA/PBAT/ Pinewood fiber strands

Lightness of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands were measured using a color reader (Konica Minolta, CR-10) in Lab system. Five strands were

attached together as a flat panel by scotch tapes, and used them as a specimen for lightness measurement. Twenty specimens for each fabrication condition were measured the lightness for calculation the average and standard deviation.

2.6 Tensile testing of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands

Tensile properties of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands were determined in accordance to ASTM D2256 using a universal testing machine (Instron 5969, USA) with a crosshead speed of 50 mm/min and 10 cm gauge length. Ten specimens of each fabrication condition were used for tensile testing, and the average and standard deviation was calculated.

2.7 Thermal properties of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands by DSC

Thermal properties of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands were determined under nitrogen atmosphere using a differential scanning calorimeter (DSC, Mettler DSC 1). The sample weight used was approximately 5-10 mg weight. The samples were tested in a heat-cool-heat mode, with the heating rate and the cooling rate of 5 °C/min. Temperature scan was performed from 30 °C to 180 °C.

2.8 Morphology study of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands by SEM

Morphology of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands were examined by a scanning electron microscope (SEM) (Jeol, JSM 5410LV). Specimens were cryo-fractured in liquid nitrogen. The cross-section of fractured surface was gold coated prior to inspection to avoid electrostatic charging.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Appearance and diameter measurement

Appearance of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands that could be viewed in naked eyes is presented in Fig.1. Composition of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/ Pinewood fiber strand was formulated to mimic color of natural rattan strands. Fig.2 shows lightness (L) of WPC strand specimens measured by a color reader. It is found that the lightness in each fabrication condition varied slightly even though PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands were produced using the same composition. Fig.3 shows the average diameters of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands in each fabrication condition, which they varied significantly by fabrication conditions. Basically, strand diameter was smaller when puller

speed was increased under constant die temperature. It should be noted that strand diameters fluctuated significantly when extruded at die temperature higher than 160 °C. The biggest strand diameter was obtained when fabricated under the highest water

bath temperature and the lowest puller speed, which the diameter was bigger than 4 mm due to extrudate swell (elastic effect). In contrast, strand diameters were the smallest when fabricated under the highest puller speed and the low water bath temperature.

Fig. 1. Appearance of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands fabricated under the L9 fabrication parameters.

Fig. 2. Lightness of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands.

Fig. 3. Diameter of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands.

Table 2. Significance of fabrication parameters for lightness and diameter

Fabrication parameters	Mean S/N ratio			Significance of fabrication parameters Max - Min
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	
Lightness				
T _{die}	26.78	25.92	25.25	1.52
T _{water}	24.56	25.90	28.11	2.92
S _{puller}	23.24	28.11	26.60	4.87
Diameter				
T _{die}	32.30	35.93	37.26	4.96
T _{water}	33.05	37.91	34.54	4.86
S _{puller}	32.06	34.93	38.50	6.44

Note: T_{die} = die temperature
 T_{water} = water bath temperature
 S_{puller} = puller speed

In Table 2, significance of fabrication parameters (difference between max. and min. values) indicates that puller speed is significantly contributing towards lightness and diameter as difference gives the highest values. Therefore, the most influencing parameter for lightness and diameter of PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands is puller speed.

3.2 Tensile and thermal properties of PLA/PBAT/ Pinewood fiber strands

Fig.4 shows stress-strain curves of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands fabricated under the L9 conditions. The stress-strain curves showed yielding after elastic deformation of the strand specimens, and then broken at strain below 0.32, except strands fabricated at D170W30S1 (condition

G) that the strand specimens were broken at strain of more than 0.5. Blending PBAT into PLA produces the blend that is much more flexible than brittle PLA. However, the presence of wood fibers causes the composite to be broken at the interface between polymer matrix and wood fibers even the good interfacial adhesion between polymer matrix and fibers is obtained as seen in SEM Images. Fig.5 presents Young's modulus of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands. It is seen that Young's modulus was in the higher range when fabricated using the die temperature of 170 °C. This is correlated well with the highest percentage of crystallinity of PLA obtained as presented in Table 3 (DSC results). It is well known that PLA crystallizes with a relatively slow crystallization rate. Under the

fabrication condition at high die temperature, the orientation of PLA molecules by stresses introduced from a puller were achieved and retained from relatively slower cooling rate. The combination of orientation and slow cooling yielded higher percentage of crystallinity. Also, the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the strands fabricated at the higher die temperature is higher than those fabricated at the lower ones. It indicates that PLA molecules had interaction with PBAT which PBAT acted as nucleating agents in PLA matrix to promote crystallization during the orientation-then-cooling mechanism. Nevertheless, the crystal structures of PLA would not be affected by the interaction between them since the melting temperature (T_m) of PLA is in the same range.

Fig. 4. Stress-strain curve of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands.

Table 3. Thermal properties of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands by DSC technique.

Fabrication Condition	T_g (°C)	T_{cc} (°C)	T_m (°C)	% Crystallinity
D160W30S0.6	57.47	91.67	153.27	27.74
D160W35S0.8	58.49	91.17	152.60	28.26
D160W40S1.0	59.33	91.25	153.76	30.53
D165W30S0.8	60.06	91.17	154.18	29.62
D165W35S1.0	60.77	89.69	152.44	26.10
D165W40S0.6	60.84	89.68	152.77	28.91
D170W30S1.0	61.09	89.68	153.18	28.87
D170W35S0.6	62.57	90.18	152.44	32.02
D170W40S0.8	62.60	89.60	153.93	32.64

Note: T_g = Glass transition temperature T_{cc} = Cold crystallization temperature
 T_m = Crystalline melting temperature

Fig. 5. Young's modulus of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands.

Fig. 6. Stress at yield of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands.

Fig. 7. Elongation at yield of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands.

Fig.6 and Fig.7 show the stress at yield and elongation at yield of the strands, respectively. We were interested in the yielding since it would dictate the failure for its function as materials for furniture production. It is found that the stress at yield was almost not affected by the fabrication conditions, except strands fabricated at D160W30S0.6 that had the lowest stress at yield. There were small voids observed (Fig.8) when strands were cooled at 30 °C. This is due to the shock cooling of the composite strands created vacuum voids resulting from inside shrinkage while the already-rigid surface inhibited any shrinkage. For elongation at yield, a correlation between elongation at yield and strand diameter is obviously observed. The highest elongation at break occurred with the strand specimens that had the largest diameter as seen in Fig.3.

Table 4. Significance of fabrication parameters for Young's modulus, tensile stress and elongation at yield.

Fabrication parameters	Mean S/N ratio			Significance of fabrication parameters Max - Min
	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	
Young's modulus				
T _{die}	30.92	31.64	27.63	4.00
T _{water}	24.94	35.31	29.94	10.38
S _{puller}	27.61	32.88	29.70	5.26
Tensile stress at yield				
T _{die}	6.098	7.065	2.431	4.634
T _{water}	8.084	4.628	2.882	5.202
S _{puller}	1.004	8.730	5.859	7.726
Elongation at yield				
T _{die}	7.991	13.983	5.399	8.584
T _{water}	10.290	8.734	8.349	1.940
S _{puller}	4.187	10.286	12.900	8.713

Note: T_{die} = die temperature,
T_{water} = water bath temperature
S_{puller} = puller speed

Significance of fabrication parameters (difference between max. and min. values) indicates that water bath temperature is significantly contributing towards Young's modulus as difference gives the highest values (Table 4). Therefore, the most influencing parameter for Young's modulus of biodegradable woo-plastic composite strand is water bath temperature. Similarly to diameter, significance of fabrication parameters (difference between max. and min. values) indicates that puller speed is the

most influencing parameter towards tensile strength and elongation at break as difference gives the highest values (Table 3).

Fig.8. Cryo-fractured SEM images of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands fabricated at D160W30S0.6 (scale bar is 3 mm).

3.3 Morphology of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands

SEM micrographs of the cryo-fractured surface of the composite strands are displayed in Figure 9A-9I. In this research, PBAT is blended in lower contents, thus the round dispersed phases are PBAT which is seen as small spheres embedded in the continuous PLA phases. Since the specimens were cryo-fractured, debonding of the round PBAT particles from the PLA matrix was not observed even though these polymers have been reported as incompatibility between them [2]. All SEM micrographs of PLA/PBAT blend depicted toughening mechanism of the polymer matrix. Usually, PLA cryo-fracture surface shows brittle failure which is smooth cut without ripples.

Fig.9. Cryo-fractured SEM images of biodegradable PLA/PBAT/Pinewood fiber strands fabricated at various conditions. (1,500X magnification).

Considering the Pinewood fibers embedded in polymer matrix, it is seen that the APES-treated wood fibers are surrounded by the polymer blend with good interfacial adhesion is observed. This indicates that amino silane used in the wood fiber treatment provides better chemical interaction between wood fibers and polymer matrix [5]. The fibers are well wetted by the polymer matrix and withdrawing of the fiber from matrix is minimized or it may even say that there is no fiber pulling out of the matrix.

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